

The Straight Paths of Universe Movement

Sir Newton's Mistake

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INTRODUCTION

Science has advanced a lot, man has set foot on the Moon, sent exploration vehicles to Mars, and even sent probes to study the Sun. Yet, human beings still remain unsuccessful in fully understanding the movements of the universe. The main reason for this is that the shortcomings of the existing laws of universal motion have not been properly studied.

If we studies Newton's laws of motion, Einstein's theory, and quantum theory in detail, any person can understand the general nature of matter. Through logical reasoning and studies of many existing theories, I have been able to understand the general nature of matter, and I am presenting before you a law of motion based on it. Through this law of motion, it is possible to explain any movement in the universe that is the benefit awaiting the future scientific world.

We must realize that based on the general nature of matter, our solar systems were formed through a great explosion. When large quantities of material particles exert pressure forces in different directions, the central region heats up and explode. When the material particles scatter and spread in different directions, in order to exist independently, they acquire a spherical shape due to the forces acting in various directions. Moreover, based on their mass, they create precise orbital distances.

The energy that is absorbed into substances under different states of heat is the energy that human beings can utilize. If that is so, then we cannot say $E = mc^2$ at this time. Instead, it can be said that $M - H = \text{Repulsive Matter} + \text{Pressure Force and Heat}$.

That is, in different states of heat and in the presence of chemical fires, repulsive matter unites to form substances that are the essence. In that case, light is merely a medium or means of exchange of matter. It cannot be said that light is the source of all energy.

With the existing theories, there still remain countless unanswered questions in astrophysics and physics, such as the Bermuda Triangle, magnetic hills, satellite orbital paths, the motion of neutron stars, the movement of asteroids, orbital shifts of planets, and the burning of the Sun. The law of motion I have put forward provides scientific answers to all of these. I strongly believe this will surely benefit the scientific world in the future.

20/01/15
अनन्ता भंडारी

Sir Isaac Newton's Mistake

Does the Earth attract all objects? Never, if so, what is gravity?

Is the origin of energy from the sun? Never, then from where?

Moving objects keep moving in an unresisted state, but attraction is a state of being resisted, yet all the planets are moving, how is that possible?

What is black energy is there such a thing?

To get an accurate answer to many such questions, we must recognize the general nature of matter. There are five general properties of matter. It is given below as a law of motion.

1. Every object in the universe, while trying to maintain itself in this universe, will also exert a force on the stationary object. This condition can be called mass.
2. Every object in the universe, when heated in its free state, will try to move away from the stationary object.
3. Every object in the universe will move to favourable areas to establish itself in a free state.
4. Every object in the universe can form an orbit around a stationary object at a precise distance according to the weight of the Free State.
5. Every object in the universe can come together and move apart under favourable conditions, which can be due to different conditions of temperature. Pressure from the outside and chemical reactions.

Let's do two simple experiments

Let's do some simple experiments. Take a syringe, fill it with atmospheric air and connect its nozzle to a pressure meter. Then press the syringe with your finger. Then observe the change in pressure inside it. From this experiment, you will understand that liquid particles have the property of pressure.

Take filler and fill it with water. It then flows out in drops. Don't you notice that this water drop tries to achieve a globe shape? Why is that? Do you notice that it exerts a force on its surroundings as part of trying to maintain itself in the region where it is located? All the planets in the universe have transformed from a liquid state to a solid state. Therefore, we have noticed that

2020/11/15
अनार्या पेंडिंग

all the planets have acquired the shape of a globe as part of exerting a force on their surroundings.

It is necessary to judge that many solar systems were formed through a big bang based on the general nature of matter. Black holes are large regions where various types of matter particles come together. Since their outer part is filled with matter particles, it is never possible to see the inner part, which will appear dark. However, according to the general

nature of matter, its interior will be a larva that is burning to a greater extent than the sun. If the temperature inside it becomes too high, a big explosion may occur according to the nature of matter. In this explosion, the larva that scatters in different directions tries to survive by applying forces in different directions, which helps it to take the shape of a globe. In addition,

the general nature of matter allows it to continue moving towards a favourable area. If attraction never controls the speed of the universe, the movement of the universe will never be possible.

heavily, the rain drops fall

Now let us learn about some of the common natural phenomena of water. Snow is a sight that we all like, where we can see water droplets moving very close together like a puff of smoke. But when it drizzling rain, the droplets of rain fall more or less evenly, and when it rains heavily, the rain drops fall unevenly and the distance between droplets are

more. Have you seen hail? It is like throwing pebbles around. Don't you notice that small and large water droplets maintain their proper spacing according to their size? The reason for this is that every object exerts a force on other sides as part of its own self-sustaining force according to the amount of its weight.

Now let's think about our solar system.

The sun, as part of its own existence, keeps exerting a force towards the centre of the solar system. But all the planets that are around the sun are also exerting a force towards the sun. The sun and all the other planets together Keep exerting a force towards this universe. Therefore, all the planets do not move away from the sun and remain part of the solar system. This happens because of the general nature of matter, not attraction. The fact that the solar system continues to move in a never-ending motion is also because of the general nature of

2021/5
अनन्ता पेंडिंग

matter. A very clear proof of this is the phenomenon of the tides that occur on our earth in relation to the moon. If attraction is taking place, this phenomenon is likely to happen only once in a day, according to the arrival of the moon. But this phenomenon happens twice. The moon has only one-fourth of its surface area facing the earth, so the force exerted by the moon on the earth by its field creates tides on two sides of the earth.

For example, if you fill a large container with water and put a ball in it and press it slightly, the

water will naturally rise in other areas. This is how the moon passes by two sides of earth and causes low tide and high tide on earth. The force exerted by the moon on the earth by its field is the reason why the earth and the moon do not come close to each other but travel at a certain distance. When the earth heats up as a whole, if the moon moves away due to the influence of the earth's field, a very strong low pressure will be formed on the earth. The return journey of the moon moving away in this way as part of maintaining its natural orbital path will cause a very strong pressure on the earth. If the inner layers of the

earth move away from each other under such pressure, it will also cause very strong earthquakes.

Let us introduce some facts related to the burning of the sun.

The interior of our Earth is formed into many layers. At the bottom is the larva that has ignited like the sun in the liquid state. This kind of combustion in the core is possible due to the force exerted by the mater particles from the outer part of the Earth to the centre of the Earth. The combustion of the Sun is caused by the force exerted by all the planets, satellites, asteroids, and dwarf planets in the solar system. If you take a bulb and

give it the right amount of electrical resistance, it will continue to burn. If you give more electricity, it will immediately become a fuse. All the planets together provide the right amount of pressure to the Sun to ignite. In the case of the Earth, the pressure required to ignite is not received from the outer part in the same amount as is required for the combustion to occur. Therefore, only the centre of the Earth is subjected to combustion. Therefore, since the

combustion on sun because of the pressure, it is never possible to say that the Sun is the source of energy. Since it is energy received from the outside, energy is only converted from one form to another. We apply pressure, and in return we get heat and light energy. Energy is not created new. It is not possible to create or destroy energy.

We have studied about comets that are moving rapidly without a precise centre in the universe. If the phenomenon of attraction is taking place, these stars will never be able to form and obtain the energy required to continue their journey. They will burn up in the region they are traveling and disappear very quickly. The reason why this does not happen is because of the force between the field of the objects in the region they are traveling and the field of the star.

Earth's orbital motion and elliptical motion

The Earth has two poles. The two poles have different mass. Therefore, the force applied to the Sun is also different. The reason why the Earth's axis is tilted is also due to this difference

in mass. Due to the tilt of the Earth's axis, the force exerted is greater when the more massive part and the less massive part face the Sun, which is the reason why the Earth's journey becomes elliptical. Similarly, when the more massive part of the Earth faces the Sun, it causes that part to move away from the Sun, which is why the elliptical motion is

also possible. When traveling in an elliptical shape, the path of travel slowly turns, and only when the more massive part faces the Sun very slowly. Therefore, the elliptical motion occurs every three months. All these movements are the cause of the Earth's seasonal changes

Now let's think about the state of matter moving away from a stationary object when it heats up and the related atmospheric movements and air pressure.

Take a transparent bottle of water and place a flame in the middle of it. Don't you notice that a flow forms in the water? Have you seen that the particles of matter rise straight up from the heated area and come down along the sides? When we heat up, we see that the particles of matter move towards the favourable area. And we can recognize two facts that they try to move away from the Earth? We know that the

atmosphere is filled with various gases, ions and microscopic elements around us. What will happen when all these gases are heated together at the same time? They will rise very quickly

2020
अनार्या पेंडिंग

from the stationary object. Then a neutral zone will be created there. According to the general nature of matter, matter particles move only towards the favourable region as part of their stability. If repulsive matter particles flow from different directions into neutral regions, when they collide with each other, a powerful cyclone will be formed. We know that rain comes with wind.

When talking about rain, we need to talk about the atomic structure of water. Water is made up of two hydrogen atoms and one oxygen. We have learned about the electron configuration of atoms and how they keep their distance from each other. Rain is caused by changes in this field under various conditions. In detail, when heated, air flows through the atoms because the particles of matter want to stay away from each other, and because they want to stay away from each other in a free state.

The speed of this flow is proportional to the amount of water vapours and gases that rise into the atmosphere. When the water vapour that rises in this way forms an orbit at a certain distance in the atmosphere and travels, it combines

with other substances in the atmosphere and transforms into raindrops due to the force exerted on the water vapours. Since the mass of raindrops is high, their free state is very high. Therefore, the air pressure above the vapour causes them to return to the earth. This is how rain is formed. Due to the force exerted by the particles of matter as part of the object

on which they stand and push them towards the solar system, only when they reach their free state can they remain in space without returning. Otherwise, they will have to become part of the earth. We know that if an object reaches a region in the outer sky where there are no particles of matter, they will continue to orbit the earth as part of the object on which they stand. When the two questions of why? How? And logical thoughts come together, theories are given shape. With the support of science, it becomes science. Some of the scientific theories thus formulated have been put forward as the law of motion of the universe. Let us think about the phenomena taking place in living beings with this law of motion. Let us first examine how the process of breathing takes place according to this theory. What a great artist God is, isn't it? We should pay attention to the shape of our respiratory tract. Isn't the part up to the respiratory tract a pipe through which air can move without any obstruction? And from the top of the chest to the bottom, the bones are arranged in a special way to form a chamber, right? All this is not

2020/11/15
आनन्द पंडित

built for nothing, you hear. What is done here is to provide an opportunity for the carbon compounds flowing through our blood to combine with oxygen. When the carbon compounds in the blood combine with oxygen, carbon dioxide and heat are produced. When heat and carbon dioxide are produced at the same time, the volume of carbon dioxide will be high, so substance produced has to go out very quickly. Due to the peculiarity of the chest cavity, the external air quickly passes into the empty lungs. It continues to work by mixing with the organic compounds. The reason for this is that the matter particles try to move to favourable areas. How precisely God has built the chest cavity in a way that is favourable for breathing, right? Such combinations in the lungs provide the necessary pressure for the heart to function. There is a yoga asana in which those who practice yoga control their breathing and pump blood to various parts of the body. Those who practice yoga are able to do this by controlling their breathing and giving pressure to the field of matter.

It can be recognized that this theory works in many other ways in living organisms

The feelings of fear, fearlessness, love, and hate are all related to this theory. It is because of

the general nature of the matter in us that we try to run away in order to escape from adverse situations and try to hold on to everything in favourable situations. When we are cold, we feel like loving everything, but when we

are violent, we try to push everything away. This is also the nature of the matter that we contain

Atoms are the smallest particles of matter. We have learned about the electron configuration of atoms and their fields. An object is formed by many atoms coming together. The field of the object will be very large. The entire world is filled with the field of such large objects. This field energy is black energy

Warning

The above points out the terrible natural disasters that global warming is going to bring to this earth. Terrible hurricanes, earthquakes, tsunamis, heat waves, and the associated forest fires are going to become commonplace on this earth. To stop this, the world must work by increasing renewable energy production, eliminating atomic energy, and controlling the combustion of diesel and petrol products, otherwise everyone must be prepared to die in natural disasters.

2020/11/15
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